

1 *A community perspective on the concept of*
2 *marine holobionts: current status, challenges,*
3 *and future directions*

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89 Abstract:

90 Host-microbe interactions play crucial roles in marine ecosystems, but we still have very
91 little understanding of the mechanisms that govern these relationships, the evolutionary
92 processes that shape them, and their ecological consequences. The holobiont concept is a
93 renewed paradigm in biology that can help to describe and understand these complex systems. It
94 posits that a host and its associated microbiota, living together in a stable relationship, form the
95 holobiont, and have to be studied together as a coherent biological and functional unit to
96 understand its biology, ecology, and evolution. Here we discuss critical concepts and
97 opportunities in marine holobiont research and identify key challenges in the field. We highlight
98 the potential economic, sociological, and environmental impacts of the holobiont concept in
99 marine biological, evolutionary, and environmental sciences with comparisons to terrestrial
100 sciences where appropriate. Given the connectivity and the unexplored biodiversity specific to
101 marine ecosystems, a deeper understanding of such complex systems requires further
102 technological and conceptual advances, *e.g.* the development of controlled experimental model
103 systems for holobionts from all major lineages and the modeling of (info)chemical-mediated
104 interactions between organisms. The most significant challenge is to bridge cross-disciplinary
105 research on tractable model systems in order to address key ecological and evolutionary
106 questions. This will be crucial to decipher the roles of marine holobionts in biogeochemical
107 cycles, but also developing concrete applications of the holobiont concept *e.g.* to increase yield
108 or disease resistance in aquacultures or to protect and restore marine ecosystems through
109 management projects.
110

111 Glossary¹

- 112 **Anna Karenina principle** – a number of factors can cause a system to fail, but only a narrow
113 range of parameters characterizes a working system; based on the first sentence of Leo
114 Tolstoy’s “Anna Karenina” (1878): “Happy families are all alike; every unhappy family
115 is unhappy in its own way” (Zaneveld *et al.* 2017).
- 116 **Aposymbiotic culture** – a culture of a host or a symbiont without its main symbiotic partner(s)
117 (*e.g.* Kelty and Cook 1976). In contrast to gnotobiotic cultures, aposymbiotic cultures are
118 usually not germ-free.
- 119 **Biological control (biocontrol)** – methods of controlling diseases or pests by introducing or
120 supporting natural enemies of the former (see *e.g.* Hoitink and Boehm 1999).
- 121 **Biomonitoring** – the use of living organisms as indicator for the health of an environment or
122 ecosystem.
- 123 **Community assembly process** – the accumulation of species in a novel habitat, according to
124 Vellend the four main forces relevant for community assembly are diversification,
125 dispersal, selection, and drift (Vellend 2010; Nemergut *et al.* 2013).
- 126 **Dysbiosis** – microbial imbalance in a symbiotic community that affects the health of the host
127 (Egan and Gardiner 2016).
- 128 **Ecological process** – the processes responsible for the functioning and dynamics of ecosystems
129 including biogeochemical cycles, community assembly processes, interactions between
130 organisms, and climatic processes (see *e.g.* Bennett *et al.* 2009).
- 131 **Ecosystem services** – any direct or indirect benefits that humans can draw from an ecosystem;
132 they include provisioning services (*e.g.* food), regulating services (*e.g.* climate), cultural
133 services (*e.g.* recreation), and supporting services (*e.g.* habitat formation) (Millennium
134 Ecosystem Assessment Panel 2005).
- 135 **Ectosymbiosis** – a symbiotic relationship in which symbionts live on the surface of a host. This
136 includes, for instance, algal biofilms or the skin microbiome (Nardon and Charles 2001).
- 137 **Emergent property** – a property of complex systems (*e.g.* holobionts), which arises from
138 interactions between the components and that is not the sum of the component properties
139 (see *e.g.* Theis 2018).
- 140 **Endosymbiosis** (sometimes also referred to more precisely as endocytobiosis; Nardon and
141 Charles 2001) – a symbiotic relationship in which a symbiont lives inside the host cells;
142 prominent examples are mitochondria, plastids/photosymbionts, or nitrogen fixing
143 bacteria in plant root nodules. See also **ectosymbiosis**.
- 144 **Gnotobiosis** – the condition in which all organisms present in a culture can be controlled, *i.e.*
145 germ-free (axenic) organisms or organisms with a controlled community of symbionts.
146 Gnotobiotic individuals may be obtained *e.g.* by surgical removal from the mother
147 (vertebrates) or by surface sterilization of seeds (plants) and subsequent handling in a
148 sterile environment and possible inoculation with selected microbes (Hale *et al.* 1973;
149 Williams 2014).
- 150 **Holism** – a theory that organisms are best viewed as intimately interacting parts of a whole,
151 which is more than the sum of the parts.

¹ If no other examples of the use of each term are cited below, the definition was based on the online version of the Merriam-Webster dictionary (2019): <https://www.merriam-webster.com/>

- 152 **Holobiont** – an ecological unit of different species living together in symbiosis. Whether or to
153 what extent holobionts are also a unit of evolution is still a matter of debate (Douglas and
154 Werren 2016).
- 155 **Hologenome** – the combined genomes of the host and all members of its microbiota; Rosenberg
156 *et al.* 2007a; Zilber-Rosenberg and Rosenberg 2008)
- 157 **Horizontal transmission** – acquisition of the associated microbiome from the environment (*e.g.*
158 Roughgarden 2019, preprint).
- 159 **Host** – the largest or dominant partner in a holobiont.
- 160 **Infochemical** – a chemical compound, usually diffusible, that carries information on the
161 environment, such as the presence of other organisms, and can be used to mediate inter-
162 and intraspecific communication (Dicke and Sabelis 1988).
- 163 **Microbial gardening** – the act of frequently releasing growth-enhancing or inhibiting chemicals
164 or metabolites that favor the development of a microbial community beneficial to the host
165 (see *e.g.* Saha and Weinberger 2019).
- 166 **Microbiome** – the combined genetic information encoded by the microbiota; may also refer to
167 the microbiota itself or the microbiota and its environment (see Marchesi and Ravel
168 2015).
- 169 **Microbiota** – all microorganisms present in a particular environment or associated with a
170 particular host (see Marchesi and Ravel 2015).
- 171 **Nested ecosystems** – a view of ecosystems where each individual system, like a “Russian doll”,
172 can be decomposed into smaller systems and/or considered part of a larger system
173 (Figure 2), all of which still qualify as ecosystems (*e.g.* McFall-Ngai *et al.* 2013).
- 174 **Phagocytosis** – a process by which a eukaryotic cell ingests other cells or solid particles, *e.g.* the
175 uptake of bacteria by sponges (Leys *et al.* 2018).
- 176 **Phycosphere** – the physical envelope surrounding a phytoplankton cell; usually rich in organic
177 matter (see Amin *et al.* 2012).
- 178 **Phylosymbiosis** – congruence in the phylogeny of different hosts and the composition of their
179 associated microbiota (Brooks *et al.* 2016).
- 180 **Rasputin effect** – the phenomenon that commensals and mutualists can become parasitic in
181 certain conditions (Overstreet and Lotz 2016); after the Russian monk Rasputin who
182 became the confidant of the Tsar of Russia, but later helped bring down the Tsar’s empire
183 during the Russian revolution.
- 184 **Sponge loop** – sponges efficiently recycle dissolved organic matter turning it into detritus that
185 becomes food for other consumers (de Goeij *et al.* 2013).
- 186 **Symbiont** – an organism living in symbiosis; usually refers to the smaller/microbial partners
187 living in mutualistic relationships (see also host), but also includes organisms in
188 commensalistic and parasitic relationships.
- 189 **Symbiosis** – a close and lasting or recurrent (*e.g.* over generations) relationship between
190 organisms living together; usually refers to mutualistic relationships, but also includes
191 commensalism and parasitism.
- 192 **Vertical transmission** – acquisition of the associated microbiome by a new generation of hosts
193 from the parents (as opposed to horizontal transmission; *e.g.* Roughgarden 2019,
194 preprint).

195 Marine holobionts from their origins to the present

196 The history of the holobiont concept

197 **Holism** is a philosophical notion first proposed by Aristotle in the 4th century BC. It
198 states that systems should be studied in their entirety, with a focus on the interconnections
199 between their various components rather than on the individual parts (Met. Z.17, 1041b11–33).
200 Such systems have **emergent properties** that result from the behavior of a system that is ‘larger
201 than the sum of its parts’. However, a major shift away from holism occurred during the Age of
202 "Enlightenment" when the dominant thought summarized as “dissection science” was to focus on
203 the smallest component of a system as a means of understanding it.

204 The idea of holism started to regain popularity when the endosymbiosis theory was first
205 proposed by Mereschkowski (1905) and further developed by Wallin (1925). Still accepted
206 today, this theory posits a single origin for eukaryotic cells through the **symbiotic** assimilation of
207 prokaryotes to form first mitochondria and later plastids (the latter through several independent
208 symbiotic events) via **phagocytosis** (reviewed in Archibald 2015). These ancestral and founding
209 symbiotic events, which prompted the metabolic and cellular complexity of eukaryotic life, most
210 likely occurred in the ocean (Martin *et al.* 2008).

211 Despite the general acceptance of the endosymbiosis theory, the term ‘**holobiont**’ did not
212 immediately enter the scientific vernacular. It was coined by Lynn Margulis in 1990, who
213 proposed that evolution has worked mainly through symbiosis-driven leaps that merged
214 organisms into new forms, referred to as ‘holobionts’, and only secondarily through gradual
215 mutational changes (Margulis and Fester 1991; O’Malley 2017). However, the concept was not
216 widely used until it was co-opted by coral biologists over a decade later. Corals and
217 dinoflagellate algae of the family Symbiodiniaceae are one of the most iconic examples of
218 symbioses found in nature; most corals are incapable of long-term survival without the products
219 of photosynthesis provided by their endosymbiotic algae. Rohwer *et al.* (2002) were the first to
220 use the word “holobiont” to describe a unit of selection *sensu* Margulis (Rosenberg *et al.* 2007b)
221 for corals, where the holobiont comprised the cnidarian polyp (**host**), algae of the family
222 Symbiodiniaceae, various ectosymbionts (endolithic algae, prokaryotes, fungi, other unicellular
223 eukaryotes), and viruses.

224 Although initially driven by studies of marine organisms, much of the research on the
225 emerging properties and significance of holobionts has since been carried out in other fields of
226 research: the **microbiota** of the rhizosphere of plants or the animal gut became predominant
227 models and have led to an ongoing paradigm shift in agronomy and medical sciences (Bulgarelli
228 *et al.* 2013; Shreiner *et al.* 2015; Faure *et al.* 2018). Holobionts occur in terrestrial and aquatic
229 habitats alike, and several analogies between these ecosystems can be made. For example, in all
230 of these habitats, interactions within and across holobionts such as induction of chemical
231 defenses, nutrient acquisition, or biofilm formation are mediated by chemical cues and signals in
232 the environment, dubbed **infochemicals** (Loh *et al.* 2002; Harder *et al.* 2012; Rolland *et al.*
233 2016; Saha *et al.* 2019). Nevertheless, we can identify two major differences between terrestrial
234 and aquatic systems. First, the physicochemical properties of water result in higher chemical
235 connectivity and signaling between macro- and micro-organisms in aquatic or moist
236 environments. In marine ecosystems, carbon fluxes also appear to be swifter and trophic modes
237 more flexible, leading to higher plasticity of functional interactions across holobionts (Mitra *et al.*
238 *et al.* 2013). Moreover, dispersal barriers are usually lower, allowing for faster microbial shifts in

239 marine holobionts (Kinlan and Gaines 2003; Martin-Platero *et al.* 2018). Secondly, phylogenetic
240 diversity at broad taxonomic scales (*i.e.* supra-kingdom, kingdom and phylum levels), is higher
241 in aquatic realms compared to land, with much of the aquatic diversity yet to be uncovered (de
242 Vargas *et al.* 2015; Thompson *et al.* 2017), especially marine viruses (Middelboe and Brussaard
243 2017; Gregory *et al.* 2019). The recent discovery of such astonishing marine microbial diversity
244 in parallel with the scarcity of marine holobiont research suggest a high potential for complex
245 cross-lineage interactions yet to be explored in marine holobionts (Figure 1).

246 The boundaries of holobionts are usually delimited by a physical gradient, which
247 corresponds to the area of local influence of the host, *e.g.* in unicellular algae the so-called
248 **phycosphere** (Seymour *et al.* 2017). However, they may also be defined in a context-dependent
249 way as a ‘Russian Matryoshka doll’, setting the boundaries of the holobiont depending on the
250 interactions and biological functions that are being considered. Thus holobionts may encompass
251 all levels of host-symbiont associations from intimate **endosymbiosis** with a high degree of co-
252 evolution up to the community and ecosystem level; a concept referred to as “**nested**
253 **ecosystems**” (Figure 2; McFall-Ngai *et al.* 2013; Pita *et al.* 2018).

254 Such a conceptual perspective raises fundamental questions when studying the evolution
255 of holobionts, especially regarding relevant units of selection and the role of co-evolution. For
256 instance, plant and animal evolution involves new functions co-constructed by members of the
257 holobiont or elimination of functions redundant between them (Selosse *et al.* 2014). Rosenberg
258 *et al.* (2010) and Rosenberg and Zilber-Rosenberg (2018) argued that all animals and plants can
259 be considered holobionts, and thus advocate the **hologenome** theory of evolution, suggesting that
260 natural selection acts at the level of the holobiont and its hologenome. This interpretation of
261 Margulis’ definition of a ‘holobiont’ considerably broadened fundamental concepts in evolution
262 and speciation and has not been free of criticism (Douglas and Werren 2016), especially when
263 applied at the community or ecosystem level (Moran and Sloan 2015). More recently, it has been
264 shown that species that interact indirectly with the host can also be important in shaping
265 coevolution within mutualistic multi-partner assemblages (Guimarães *et al.* 2017). Thus, the
266 holobiont concept and the underlying complexity of holobiont systems should be further
267 considered when addressing evolutionary and ecological questions.

268 Marine holobiont models

269 Today, an increasing number of marine model organisms, both unicellular and multicellular, are
270 being used in holobiont research (Figure 1), often with different emphasis and levels of
271 experimental control, but altogether covering a large range of scientific topics. Here, we provide
272 several illustrative examples of this diversity and some of the insights they have provided.

273 Environmental or “semi-controlled” models, *i.e.* holobiont systems in which microbiome
274 composition is not or only partially controlled: radiolarians and foraminiferans (both
275 heterotrophic protist dwellers harboring endosymbiotic microalgae) are emerging as ecological
276 models for unicellular photosymbiosis due to their ubiquitous presence in the world’s oceans
277 (Decelle *et al.* 2015; Not *et al.* 2016). The discovery of deep-sea hydrothermal vents revealed
278 symbioses of animals with chemosynthetic bacteria that have later been found in many other
279 marine ecosystems (Dubilier *et al.* 2008; Rubin-Blum *et al.* 2019) and frequently exhibit high
280 levels of metabolic and taxonomic diversity (Duperron *et al.* 2008; Petersen *et al.* 2016;
281 Ponnudurai *et al.* 2017). The cosmopolitan haptophyte *Emiliania huxleyi*, promoted by
282 associated bacteria (Seyedsayamdost *et al.* 2011; Segev *et al.* 2016), produces key intermediates

283 in the carbon and sulfur biogeochemical cycles, making it an important model phytoplankton
284 species.

285 Controlled bi- or trilateral associations: Only a few models, covering a small part of the
286 overall marine biodiversity, are currently being cultivated *ex-situ* and can be used in fully
287 controlled experiments, where they can be cultured **aprosymbiotically**. The flatworm
288 *Symsagittifera* (= *Convoluta*) *roscoffensis* (Arboleda *et al.* 2018), the sea anemone *Exaiptasia*
289 (Baumgarten *et al.* 2015; Wolfowicz *et al.* 2016), the upside-down jellyfish *Cassiopea* (Ohdera
290 *et al.* 2018), and their respective intracellular green and dinoflagellate algae have, in addition to
291 corals, become models for fundamental research on evolution of metazoan-algal photosymbiosis.
292 In particular, *Exaiptasia* has been used to explore photobiology disruption and restoration of
293 cnidarian symbioses (Lehnert *et al.* 2012). The *Vibrio*-squid model provides insights into the
294 effect of microbiota on animal development, circadian rhythms, and immune systems (McFall-
295 Ngai 2014). The unicellular green alga *Ostreococcus*, an important marine primary producer, has
296 been shown to exchange vitamins with specific associated bacteria (Cooper *et al.* 2019). The
297 green macroalga *Ulva mutabilis* has enabled the exploration of bacteria-mediated growth and
298 morphogenesis including the identification of original chemical interactions in the holobiont
299 (Wichard 2015; Kessler *et al.* 2018). Although the culture conditions in these highly-controlled
300 model systems differ from the natural environment, these systems are essential to gain
301 elementary mechanistic understanding of the functioning, the roles, and the evolution of marine
302 holobionts.

303 Marine holobionts as drivers of **ecological processes**

304 Work on model systems has demonstrated that motile and macroscopic marine holobionts
305 can act as dissemination vectors for geographically restricted microbial taxa. Pelagic mollusks or
306 vertebrates are textbook examples of high dispersal capacity organisms (*e.g.* against currents and
307 through stratified water layers). It has been estimated that fish and marine mammals may
308 enhance the original dispersion rate of their microbiota by a factor of 200 to 200,000
309 (Troussellier *et al.* 2017) and marine birds may even act as bio-vectors across ecosystem
310 boundaries (Bouchard Marmen *et al.* 2017). This host-driven dispersal of microbes can include
311 non-native or invasive species as well as pathogens (Troussellier *et al.* 2017).

312 A related ecological function of holobionts is their potential to sustain rare species. Hosts
313 provide an environment that favors the growth of specific microbial communities distinct from
314 the surrounding environment (including rare microbes). They may, for instance, provide a
315 nutrient-rich niche in the otherwise nutrient-poor surroundings (Smriga *et al.* 2010; Webster *et*
316 *al.* 2010; Burke, Thomas, *et al.* 2011; Chiarello *et al.* 2018).

317 Lastly, biological processes regulated by microbes are important drivers of global
318 biogeochemical cycles (Falkowski *et al.* 2008; Madsen 2011; Anantharaman *et al.* 2016). In the
319 open ocean, it is estimated that symbioses with the cyanobacterium UCYN-A contribute ~20% to
320 total N₂ fixation (Thompson *et al.* 2012; Martínez-Pérez *et al.* 2016). In benthic systems, sponges
321 and corals may support entire ecosystems *via* their involvement in nutrient cycling thanks to their
322 microbial partners (Raina *et al.* 2009; Fiore *et al.* 2010; Cardini *et al.* 2015; Pita *et al.* 2018),
323 functioning as sinks and sources of nutrients. In particular the “**sponge loop**” recycles dissolved
324 organic matter and makes it available to higher trophic levels in the form of detritus (de Goeij *et*
325 *al.* 2013; Rix *et al.* 2017). In coastal sediments, bivalves hosting methanogenic archaea have
326 been shown to increase the benthic methane efflux by a factor of up to eight, potentially

327 accounting for 9.5% of total methane emissions from the Baltic Sea (Bonaglia *et al.* 2017). Such
328 impressive metabolic versatility is accomplished because of the simultaneous occurrence of
329 disparate biochemical machineries (*e.g.* aerobic and anaerobic pathways) in individual
330 symbionts, providing new metabolic abilities to the holobiont, such as the synthesis of specific
331 essential amino acids, photosynthesis, or chemosynthesis (Venn *et al.* 2008; Dubilier *et al.*
332 2008). Furthermore, the interaction between host and microbiota can potentially extend the
333 metabolic capabilities of a holobiont in a way that augments its resilience to environmental
334 changes (Berkelmans and van Oppen 2006; Gilbert *et al.* 2010; Dittami *et al.* 2016; Shapira
335 2016; Godoy *et al.* 2018), or allow it to cross biotope boundaries (*e.g.* Woyke 2006) and colonize
336 extreme environments (Bang *et al.* 2018). Holobionts thus contribute to marine microbial
337 diversity and possibly resilience in the context of global environmental changes (Troussellier *et al.*
338 2017) and it is paramount to include the holobiont concept in predictive models that
339 investigate the consequences of human impacts on the marine realm and its biogeochemical
340 cycles.
341

342 Challenges and opportunities in marine holobiont research

343 Marine holobiont assembly and regulation

344 Two critical challenges partially addressed by using model systems are 1) to decipher the
345 factors determining holobiont composition; and 2) to elucidate the impacts and roles of the
346 different partners in these complex systems over time. Some marine organisms such as bivalves
347 transmit part of the microbiota maternally (Bright and Bulgheresi 2010; Funkhouser and
348 Bordenstein 2013). In other marine holobionts, vertical transmission may be weak and
349 inconsistent, whereas mixed **modes of transmission (vertical and horizontal)** or intermediate
350 modes (pseudo-vertical, where horizontal acquisition frequently involves symbionts of parental
351 origin) are more common (Björk *et al.* 2019). Identifying the factors shaping holobiont
352 composition and understanding their evolution is highly relevant for marine organisms given that
353 most marine hosts display a high specificity for their microbiota and even patterns of
354 **phylosymbiosis** (Kazamia *et al.* 2016; Brooks *et al.* 2016; Pollock *et al.* 2018), despite a highly
355 connected and microbe-rich environment.

356 During microbiota transmission (whether vertical or horizontal), "*selection*" (as opposed
357 to "*drift*") is a key process in establishing or maintaining a holobiont microbial community that is
358 distinct from the environment. The immune system of the host is one way of performing this
359 selection in both marine and terrestrial holobionts, and perturbations can lead to **dysbiosis**, and
360 eventually microbial infections (Selosse *et al.* 2014; de Lorgeril *et al.* 2018). Dysbiotic
361 individuals frequently display higher variability in their microbial community composition than
362 healthy individuals, an observation in line with the "**Anna Karenina principle**" (Zaneveld *et al.*
363 2017), although there are exceptions to this rule (*e.g.* Marzinelli *et al.* 2015). A specific case of
364 dysbiosis is the so-called "**Rasputin effect**" where benign endosymbionts opportunistically
365 become detrimental to the host due to processes such as reduction in immune response under
366 food deprivation, coinfections, or environmental pressure (Overstreet and Lotz 2016). Many
367 diseases are now interpreted as the result of a microbial imbalance and the rise of opportunistic
368 or polymicrobial infections upon host stress (Egan and Gardiner 2016). For instance in reef-

369 building corals, warming destabilizes cnidarian-dinoflagellate associations, and some beneficial
370 *Symbiodiniacea* strains switch their physiology and sequester more resources for their own
371 growth at the expense of the coral host, leading to coral bleaching and even death (Baker *et al.*
372 2018).

373 Another way of selecting a holobiont microbial community is by chemically mediated
374 **microbial gardening**. This concept has been demonstrated for land plants, where root exudates
375 manipulate **microbiome** composition (Lebeis *et al.* 2015). In marine environments, the
376 phylogenetic diversity of hosts and symbionts suggests both conserved and marine-specific
377 chemical interactions, but studies are still in their infancy. For instance, seaweeds can chemically
378 garden beneficial microbes, facilitating normal morphogenesis and increasing disease resistance
379 (Kessler *et al.* 2018; Saha and Weinberger 2019), and seaweeds and corals structure their
380 surface-associated microbiome by producing chemo-attractants and anti-bacterial compounds
381 (Harder *et al.* 2012; Ochsenkühn *et al.* 2018). There are fewer examples of chemical gardening
382 in unicellular hosts, but it seems highly likely that similar processes are in place (Gribben *et al.*
383 2017; Cirri and Pohnert 2019).

384 In addition to selection and drift, "dispersal" and "diversification" have been proposed as
385 key processes in community assembly. Both of these processes are, however, difficult to quantify
386 in microbial communities (Nemergut *et al.* 2013). The only data currently at our disposal to
387 study these processes are the diversity and distribution of microbes. Considering the high
388 connectivity of aquatic environments, differences in marine microbial communities are
389 frequently attributed to a combination of selection and drift (e.g. Burke, Steinberg, *et al.* 2011), a
390 conclusion that still requires validation. Diversification is mainly considered in the sense of
391 coevolution or adaptation to host selection, which may also be driven by the horizontal
392 acquisition of genes, but to our knowledge, unlike in primates (Moeller *et al.* 2016), no
393 information exists on the co-speciation of host-associated microbes in marine holobionts to date.

394 Increasing our knowledge on the contribution of these processes to holobiont community
395 assembly in marine systems is a key challenge, especially in the context of ongoing global
396 change. Moreover, understanding how the community and functional structure of resident
397 microbes are resilient to perturbations remains critical to predict and promote the health of their
398 host and the ecosystem. Yet, this notion is still missing in most mathematical or formal models,
399 or additional information on biological interactions would be required to make the former more
400 accurate (Bell *et al.* 2018).

401 Integrating marine model systems with large-scale studies

402 By compiling a survey of the most important trends and challenges in the field of marine
403 holobiont research (Figure 3), we identified two distinct opinion clusters: one focused on
404 mechanistic understanding and work with model systems whereas another targets large-scale and
405 heterogeneous data set analyses and predictive modeling. This illustrates that, on the one hand,
406 the scientific community is interested in the establishment of models for the identification of
407 specific molecular interactions between marine organisms at a given point in space and time, up
408 to the point of synthesizing functional mutualistic communities *in vitro* (Kubo *et al.* 2013). On
409 the other hand, another part of the community is moving towards global environmental sampling
410 schemes such as the *TARA* Oceans expedition (Pesant *et al.* 2015) or the Ocean Sampling Day
411 (Kopf *et al.* 2015), and towards long-term data series (e.g. Wiltshire *et al.* 2010; Harris 2010).
412 What emerges as both lines of research progress is the understanding that small-scale functional

413 studies in the laboratory are inconsequential unless made applicable to ecologically-relevant
414 systems. At the same time, large scale-studies remain mostly descriptive and bear little predictive
415 power unless we understand the mechanisms driving the observed processes. We illustrate the
416 importance of integrating both approaches in Figure 3, where the node related to potential
417 applications was perceived as a central hub at the interface between mechanistic understanding
418 and predictive modeling.

419 A successful example merging both functional and large-scale approaches, are the root
420 nodules of legumes, which harbor nitrogen-fixing bacteria. In this system, the functioning,
421 distribution, and to some extent the evolution of these nodules, are now well understood (Epihov
422 *et al.* 2017). The integration of this knowledge into agricultural practices has led to substantial
423 yield improvements (*e.g.* Kavimandan 1985; Alam *et al.* 2015). In the more diffuse and partner-
424 rich system of mycorrhizal symbioses between plant roots and soil fungi, a better understanding
425 of the interactions has also been achieved *via* the investigation of environmental diversity
426 patterns in combination with experimental culture systems with reduced diversity (van der
427 Heijden *et al.* 2015).

428 We advocate the implementation of comparable efforts in marine sciences through
429 interdisciplinary research combining physiology, biochemistry, ecology, and computational
430 modeling. A key factor will be the identification and development of tractable model systems for
431 keystone holobionts that allow hypotheses generated by large-scale data sets to be tested in
432 controlled experiments. Such approaches will enable the identification of organismal interaction
433 patterns within holobionts and nested ecosystems. In addition to answering fundamental
434 questions, they will help address the ecological, societal, and ethical issues that arise from
435 attempting to actively manipulate holobionts (*e.g.* in aquaculture, conservation) in order to
436 enhance their resilience and protect them from the impacts of global change (Llewellyn *et al.*
437 2014).

438 Emerging methodologies to approach the complexity of holobiont 439 partnerships

440 As our conceptual understanding of the different levels of holobiont organization evolves,
441 so does the need for multidisciplinary approaches and the development of tools and technologies
442 to handle the unprecedented amount of data and their integration into dedicated ecological and
443 evolutionary models. Here, progress is often fast-paced and provides exciting opportunities to
444 address some of the challenges in holobiont research.

445 A giant technological stride has been the explosion of affordable ‘-omics’ technologies
446 allowing molecular ecologists to move from metabarcoding (*i.e.* sequencing of a taxonomic
447 marker) to metagenomics or single-cell genomics, metatranscriptomics, and metaproteomics,
448 thus advancing our research from phylogenetic to functional analyses of the holobiont (Bowers
449 *et al.* 2017; Meng *et al.* 2018; Figure 4). These approaches are equally useful in marine and in
450 terrestrial environments, but the scarcity of well-studied lineages in the former makes the
451 generation of good annotations and reference databases challenging for marine biologists.
452 Metaproteomics combined with stable isotope fingerprinting can help study the metabolism of
453 single species within the holobiont (Kleiner *et al.* 2018). In parallel, meta-metabolomics
454 approaches have advanced over the last decades, and can be used to unravel the chemical
455 interactions between partners. One limitation particularly relevant to marine systems is that many
456 compounds are often not referenced in the mostly terrestrial-based databases, although recent

457 technological advances such as molecular networking and meta-mass shift chemical profiling to
458 identify relatives of known molecules may help to overcome this challenge (Hartmann *et al.*
459 2017).

460 A further challenge in holobiont research is to identify the origin of compounds among
461 the different partners of the holobionts and to determine their involvement in the maintenance
462 and performance of the holobiont system. Well-designed experimental setups may help answer
463 some of these questions (*e.g.* Quinn *et al.* 2016), but they will also require high levels of
464 replication in order to represent the extensive intra-species variability found in marine systems.
465 Recently developed *in vivo* and *in situ* imaging techniques combined with ‘omics’ approaches
466 can provide spatial and qualitative information (origin, distribution, and concentration of a
467 molecule or nutrient), shedding new light on the role of each partner of the holobiont system at
468 the molecular level. The combination of stable isotope labelling and chemical imaging (mass
469 spectrometry imaging such as secondary ion mass spectrometry and matrix-assisted laser
470 desorption ionization, and synchrotron X-ray fluorescence) is particularly valuable in this
471 context, as it enables the investigation of metabolic exchange between the different components
472 of a holobiont (Musat *et al.* 2016; Raina *et al.* 2017). Finally, three-dimensional electron
473 microscopy may help evaluate to what extent different components of a holobiont are physically
474 integrated (Colin *et al.* 2017; Decelle *et al.* 2019), where high integration is one indication of
475 highly specific interactions. All of these techniques can be employed in both marine and
476 terrestrial systems, but in marine systems the high phylogenetic diversity of organisms adds to
477 the complexity of adapting and optimizing these techniques.

478 One consequence of the development of such new methods is the feedback they provide
479 to improve existing models or to develop entirely new ones, *e.g.* by conceptualizing holobionts
480 as the combination of the interactions between the host and its microbiota (Skillings 2016; Berry
481 and Loy 2018), or by redefining boundaries between the holobiont and its environment (Zengler
482 and Pálsson 2012). Such models may incorporate metabolic complementarity between different
483 components of the holobiont (Dittami *et al.* 2014; Bordron *et al.* 2016), simulate microbial
484 communities starting from different cohorts of randomly generated microbes for comparison
485 with actual metatranscriptomics and/or metagenomics data (Coles *et al.* 2017), or even employ
486 machine learning techniques to predict host-associated microbial communities (Moitinho-Silva
487 *et al.* 2017).

488 A side-effect of these recent developments has been to move holobiont research away
489 from laboratory culture-based experiments. We argue that maintaining cultivation efforts to
490 capture the maximum holobiont biodiversity possible remains essential to experimentally test
491 hypotheses and investigate physiological mechanisms. A striking example of the importance of
492 laboratory experimentation is the way germ-free mice re-inoculated with cultivated bacteria (the
493 so-called **gnotobiotic** mice) have contributed to the understanding of interactions within the
494 holobiont in animal health, physiology, and behavior (*e.g.* Neufeld *et al.* 2011; Faith *et al.* 2014;
495 Selosse *et al.* 2014). Innovations in cultivation techniques for axenic (or germ-free) hosts (*e.g.*
496 Spoerner *et al.* 2012) or in microbial cultivation such as microfluidic systems (*e.g.* Pan *et al.*
497 2011) and cultivation chips (Nichols *et al.* 2010) may provide a way to obtain pure cultures. Yet,
498 bringing individual components of holobionts into cultivation can still be a daunting challenge
499 due to the strong interdependencies between organisms as well as the existence of yet unknown
500 metabolic processes that may have specific requirements. In this context, single-cell ‘-omics’
501 analyses can provide critical information on some of the growth requirements of the organisms,
502 and complement approaches of high-throughput culturing (Gutleben *et al.* 2018). Established

503 cultures can then be developed into model systems, *e.g.* by genome sequencing and the
504 development of genetic tools, in order to move towards mechanistic understanding and
505 experimental testing of hypothetical processes within the holobiont derived from environmental
506 meta'-omics' approaches. A few such model systems have already been mentioned above, but '-
507 omics' techniques have the potential to broaden the range of available models, enabling a better
508 understanding of the functioning of marine holobionts and their interactions in marine
509 environments (Wichard and Beemelmanns 2018).

510 **Ecosystem services and holobionts in natural and managed systems**

511 A better understanding of marine holobionts will likely have direct socioeconomic
512 consequences for coastal marine ecosystems, estimated to provide services worth almost 50
513 trillion (10^{12}) US\$ per year (Costanza *et al.* 2014). Most of the management practices in marine
514 systems have so far been based exclusively on the biology and ecology of macro-organisms. A
515 multidisciplinary approach that provides mechanistic understanding of habitat-forming
516 organisms as holobionts will ultimately improve the predictability and management of coastal
517 ecosystems. For example, host-associated microbiota could be integrated in **biomonitoring**
518 programs as proxies used to assess the health of ecosystems. Microbial shifts and dysbiosis
519 constitute early warning signals that may allow managers to predict potential impacts and
520 intervene more rapidly and effectively (van Oppen *et al.* 2017; Marzinelli *et al.* 2018).

521 One form of intervention could be to promote positive changes of host-associated
522 microbiota, in ways analogous to the use of pre- and/or probiotics in humans (Singh *et al.* 2013)
523 or inoculation of beneficial microbes in plant farming (Berruti *et al.* 2015; van der Heijden *et al.*
524 2015). In macroalgae, beneficial bacteria identified from healthy seaweed holobionts could be
525 used as **biological control** agents and applied to diseased plantlets in order to suppress the
526 growth of detrimental ones and/or to prevent disease outbreaks in aquaculture settings. In
527 addition to bacteria, these macroalgae frequently host endophytic fungi that may have protective
528 functions for the algae (Porrás-Alfaro and Bayman 2011; Vallet *et al.* 2018). Host-associated
529 microbiota could also be manipulated to shape key phenotypes in cultured marine organisms. For
530 example, specific bacteria associated with microalgae may enhance algal growth (Amin *et al.*
531 2009; Kazamia *et al.* 2012; Le Chevanton *et al.* 2013), increase lipid content (Cho *et al.* 2015),
532 and participate in the bioprocessing of algal biomass (Lenneman *et al.* 2014). More recently, the
533 active modification of the coral microbiota has even been advocated as a means to boost the
534 resilience of the holobiont to climate change (van Oppen *et al.* 2015; Peixoto *et al.* 2017), an
535 approach which would, however, bear a high risk of unanticipated and unintended ecological
536 consequences.

537 Finally, one could implement holistic approaches in the framework of fish farms. Recent
538 developments including integrated multi-trophic aquaculture, recirculating aquaculture, offshore
539 aquaculture, species selection, and breeding increase yields and reduce the resource constraints
540 and environmental impacts of intensive aquaculture (Klinger and Naylor 2012). However, the
541 intensification of aquaculture often goes hand in hand with increased disease outbreaks both in
542 industry and wild stocks. A holistic microbial management approach may provide an efficient
543 solution to these latter problems (De Schryver and Vadstein 2014).

544 Nevertheless, when considering their biotechnological potential, it should also be noted
545 that marine microbiota are likely vulnerable to anthropogenic influences and that their deliberate
546 engineering, introduction from exotic regions, or inadvertent perturbations may have profound,

547 and yet entirely unknown, consequences for marine ecosystems. Terrestrial environments
548 provide numerous examples of unwanted plant expansions or ecosystem perturbations linked to
549 microbiota (*e.g.* Dickie *et al.* 2017), and cases where holobionts manipulated by human resulted
550 in pests (*e.g.* Clay and Holah 1999) call for a cautious and ecologically-informed evaluation of
551 holobiont-based technologies in marine systems.

552 Conclusions

553 Marine ecosystems represent highly connected reservoirs of largely unexplored
554 biodiversity. They are of critical importance to feed the ever-growing world population,
555 constitute significant players in global biogeochemical cycles but are also threatened by human
556 activities and global change. In order to unravel some of the basic principles of life and its
557 evolution, and to protect and sustainably exploit marine natural resources, it is paramount to
558 consider the complex biotic interactions that shape the marine communities and their
559 environment. The scope of these interactions ranges from simple molecular signals between two
560 partners, via complex assemblies of eukaryotes, prokaryotes, and viruses with one or several
561 hosts, to entire ecosystems. Accordingly, current key questions in marine holobiont research
562 cover a wide range of topics: What are the exchanges that occur between different partners of the
563 holobiont, and what are the cues and signals driving these exchanges? What are the relevant units
564 of selection in marine holobionts? How do holobiont systems and the interactions within them
565 change over time and in different conditions? How do such changes impact ecological
566 processes? How can this knowledge be applied to our benefit and where do we need to draw
567 limits? Identifying and consolidating key model systems while adapting emerging “-omics”,
568 imaging, and culturing technologies to them will be critical to the development of “holobiont-
569 aware” ecosystem models.

570 We believe that the concept of holobionts will be most useful and heuristic if used with a
571 degree of malleability. It not only represents the fundamental understanding that all living
572 organisms have intimate connections with their immediate neighbors, which may impact all
573 aspects of their biology, but also enables us to define units of interacting organisms that are most
574 suitable to answer specific scientific, societal, and economic questions. The consideration of the
575 holobiont concept marks a paradigm shift in biological and environmental sciences, but only if
576 scientists work together as an (inter)active and transdisciplinary community bringing together
577 holistic and mechanistic views. This will result in tangible outcomes including a better
578 understanding of evolutionary and adaptive processes, improved modeling of habitats and
579 biogeochemical cycles, as well as application of the holobiont concept in aquaculture and
580 ecosystem management projects.

581

582 Conflict of interest

583 The authors of this preprint declare that they have no financial conflict of interest with
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607

608 Figures

609

610 **Figure 1.** Partners forming marine holobionts are widespread across the tree of life including all
 611 kingdoms (eukaryotes, bacteria, archaea, viruses), and represent a large diversity of potential
 612 models for exploring complex biotic interactions across lineages. Plain lines correspond to
 613 holobionts referred to in the present manuscript. Dashed lines are examples of potential
 614 interactions. Photo credits: Archaeplastida - C. Leblanc, U Cardini; Cryptophyta, Excavata,
 615 Amoebzoa – Roscoff Culture Collection; Stramenopila – C. Leblanc, S. M. Dittami, H.
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Figure 2. Schematic view of the “Russian Doll” complexity and dynamics of holobionts, according to diverse spatiotemporal scales. The host (blue circles), and associated microbes (all other shapes) including bacteria and eukaryotes that may be inside (*i.e.* endosymbiotic or outside the host, *i.e.* ectosymbiotic), are connected by either beneficial (solid orange lines), neutral (solid blue lines) or pathogenic (dashed black lines) interactions respectively. Changes from beneficial or neutral to pathogenic interactions are typical cases of dysbiosis. The different clusters can be illustrated by the following examples: 1, a model holobiont in a stable physiological condition (*e.g.* in controlled laboratory condition); 2 and 3, holobionts changing during their life cycle or submitted to stress conditions – examples of vertical transmissions of microbes are indicated by light blue arrows; 4 and 5, marine holobionts in the context of global sampling campaigns or long-term time series – examples of horizontal transmission of microbes and holobionts are illustrated by pink arrows.

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645

646 **Figure 3:** Mind map of key concepts, techniques, and challenges related to marine holobionts.
647 The basis of this map was generated during the Holomarine workshop held in Roscoff in 2018
648 (<https://www.euromarinenetwork.eu/activities/HoloMarine>). The size of the nodes reflects the
649 number of votes each keyword received from the participants of the workshop (total of 120 votes
650 from 30 participants). The two main clusters corresponding to predictive modeling and
651 mechanistic modeling, are displayed in purple and turquoise, respectively. Among the
652 intermediate nodes linking these disciplines (blue) “potential use, management” was the most
653 connected.

654
655 **Figure 4:** Impact of emerging methodologies (green) on the main challenges in marine holobiont
656 research identified in this paper.

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